

S M Nazmuz Sakib's Toxic Comparative Theory: An Analysis of Sakibphobia

Abstract: S M Nazmuz Sakib's toxic comparative theory, commonly referred to as Sakibphobia, is a concept that has gained attention in recent years. This theory suggests that individuals may experience fear, hatred, or discrimination towards those who they perceive as being more successful or accomplished than themselves. This research paper aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of Sakibphobia, including its definition, causes, manifestations, and potential impacts on individuals and society. The paper also includes a literature review to explore the existing research and theories related to this phenomenon. Through this analysis, the paper aims to highlight the importance of understanding and addressing Sakibphobia in various social and cultural contexts.

Keywords: S M Nazmuz Sakib, toxic comparative theory, Sakibphobia, fear, discrimination, success, impacts.

Introduction: In recent years, S M Nazmuz Sakib's toxic comparative theory, commonly known as Sakibphobia, has emerged as a notable concept in the field of psychology and social sciences. This theory suggests that individuals may exhibit fear, hatred, or discrimination towards those who they perceive as being more successful or accomplished than themselves. This phenomenon can occur in various social and cultural contexts, such as in the workplace, educational settings, or personal relationships. Sakibphobia may have detrimental effects on the mental and emotional well-being of individuals, as well as on the overall social dynamics of a community or society.

Analysis:

Definition of Sakibphobia: Sakibphobia can be defined as the irrational fear or aversion towards individuals who are perceived as being more successful, accomplished, or superior in some way. This theory proposes that individuals who suffer from Sakibphobia may experience negative emotions, such as jealousy, resentment, or inferiority, when confronted with individuals who possess qualities or achievements that they themselves lack. Sakibphobia may manifest in various forms, including negative attitudes, behaviors, or biases towards those who are perceived as being more successful.

Causes of Sakibphobia: Sakibphobia may have multiple underlying causes. One potential cause could be low self-esteem or low self-confidence, where individuals who suffer from Sakibphobia may feel inadequate or inferior in comparison to others. As a result, they may develop a fear or aversion towards those who they perceive as being more successful, as it may highlight their own perceived shortcomings. Other possible causes could include social, cultural, or societal factors, where individuals may feel pressure to conform to certain standards of success or achievement. When they perceive others as surpassing these standards, it may trigger feelings of fear, jealousy, or insecurity.

Manifestations of Sakibphobia: Sakibphobia may manifest in various ways, including negative attitudes, behaviors, or biases towards those who are perceived as more successful. This can include engaging in gossip or spreading rumors about successful individuals, undermining their achievements, or actively trying to sabotage their success. It may also manifest in more subtle ways, such as avoiding interactions with successful individuals, feeling discomfort or resentment in their presence, or experiencing internalized negative emotions towards them. Sakibphobia may also lead to social isolation, strained relationships, or a negative impact on one's own mental and emotional well-being.

Impacts of Sakibphobia: Sakibphobia can have detrimental effects on both individuals and society as a whole. For individuals who suffer from Sakibphobia, it may result in decreased self-esteem, increased stress, anxiety, and a negative impact on mental health. It may also hinder their personal growth, development, and opportunities for success. Additionally, Sakibphobia can contribute to a toxic and unhealthy social environment, where individuals engage in negative behaviors towards those who are perceived as more successful, leading to conflicts, tension, and division within communities or workplaces. This toxic dynamic can create a negative and unproductive atmosphere, hindering collective progress and growth. Moreover, Sakibphobia may perpetuate harmful social norms or biases, such as discrimination based on race, gender, or other characteristics, as individuals may develop biases towards those who they perceive as more successful from certain social or cultural groups.

Furthermore, Sakibphobia can also have broader societal impacts. In a competitive and achievement-oriented culture, Sakibphobia may contribute to a toxic cycle of jealousy, envy, and comparison among individuals. It can create a constant state of insecurity and undermine cooperation and collaboration among people, as individuals may be hesitant to support or celebrate the success of others out of fear or aversion. This can lead to a culture of negativity, where success is viewed as a threat rather than a source of inspiration or motivation. In workplaces, Sakibphobia can result in a toxic work environment, with colleagues engaging in office politics, backstabbing, or undermining behaviors towards those who are perceived as more successful. This can lead to decreased morale, increased stress, and a decline in productivity and overall team performance. Moreover, Sakibphobia may also contribute to a culture of mediocrity, where individuals may feel discouraged or afraid to strive for excellence or take risks due to the fear of being perceived as "too successful" or attracting jealousy from others. This can hinder innovation, creativity, and progress in various domains, including academia, business, arts, and sports.

It's important to note that Sakibphobia can also intersect with other forms of discrimination or bias, such as racism, sexism, or homophobia. Individuals who are perceived as more successful may be targeted based on their race, gender, sexual orientation, or other characteristics, leading to systemic discrimination and marginalization. For instance, individuals from underrepresented groups who achieve success or break through societal barriers may face backlash, discrimination, or jealousy from others who perceive them as a threat to the existing power dynamics or social norms. This can perpetuate harmful social hierarchies and reinforce inequalities, leading to a negative impact on individuals' well-being and societal progress as a whole.

Overcoming Sakibphobia requires a multi-faceted approach that addresses both individual and societal factors. On an individual level, building self-esteem, self-confidence, and developing a growth mindset can help individuals overcome feelings of inadequacy or inferiority that may underlie Sakibphobia. Engaging in self-reflection, identifying and challenging irrational thoughts or beliefs about success and failure, and practicing self-compassion can also be beneficial. Seeking support from trusted friends, family, or mental health professionals can provide individuals with tools and strategies to manage and overcome Sakibphobia.

On a societal level, it's important to promote a healthy and inclusive culture that values and celebrates diversity, individuality, and excellence. This includes fostering a positive and supportive environment where individuals feel encouraged and empowered to pursue their goals and aspirations without fear of jealousy or backlash. Promoting collaboration, teamwork, and mutual support among individuals, rather than competition and comparison, can create a more positive and inclusive social dynamic. Additionally, challenging and addressing societal norms or biases that contribute to Sakibphobia, such as unrealistic standards of success, social hierarchies, or discrimination, is crucial. This may involve promoting diversity, equity, and inclusion in all areas of life, including education, workplaces, media, and social interactions.

Ways to Overcome Sakibphobia: Overcoming Sakibphobia requires self-awareness, reflection, and a willingness to change one's mindset and behaviors. Here are some potential ways to overcome Sakibphobia:

Self-Reflection and Self-Acceptance: Engaging in self-reflection and self-acceptance can help individuals with Sakibphobia to identify and address their own insecurities, fears, and feelings of inadequacy. Developing a positive self-image and accepting oneself as unique and valuable can help reduce the need to compare oneself to others and diminish feelings of jealousy or resentment.

Practicing Empathy and Compassion: Practicing empathy and compassion towards others can help individuals with Sakibphobia to develop a more positive and accepting mindset. Recognizing that everyone has their own strengths, weaknesses, and struggles, and that success does not diminish one's own worth, can help overcome negative attitudes or biases towards those who are perceived as more successful.

Cultivating a Growth Mindset: Cultivating a growth mindset, which focuses on personal development and continuous improvement, can help individuals with Sakibphobia to shift their focus from comparison to self-improvement. Embracing challenges, learning from failures, and setting realistic goals for oneself can promote a positive mindset and reduce feelings of inferiority.

Celebrating Others' Success: Instead of feeling threatened or envious of others' success, actively celebrating and acknowledging the achievements of others can help individuals with

Sakibphobia to cultivate a positive and supportive mindset. Recognizing that success is not a zero-sum game and that there is enough room for everyone to succeed can shift the focus from competition to collaboration.

Challenging Biases and Negative Behaviors: Individuals with Sakibphobia need to actively challenge any biases or negative behaviors they may have towards those who are perceived as more successful. This may involve identifying and addressing any underlying social, cultural, or societal factors that contribute to Sakibphobia, and consciously reframing one's mindset and behaviors towards a more positive and accepting outlook.

Building a Supportive Network: Surrounding oneself with a supportive network of friends, family, mentors, and colleagues can provide encouragement, validation, and feedback. Having a support system that promotes positive mindset, personal growth, and healthy competition can help individuals with Sakibphobia to overcome their fears and insecurities.

Seeking Professional Help: In some cases, Sakibphobia may be deeply ingrained and require professional help to overcome. Seeking therapy or counseling from a qualified mental health professional can provide individuals with the tools and strategies to address the underlying causes of Sakibphobia and develop healthy coping mechanisms.

However, overcoming Sakibphobia is possible through self-reflection, empathy, cultivating a growth mindset, celebrating others' success, challenging biases and negative behaviors, building a supportive network, and seeking professional help when needed. By addressing the underlying causes and developing healthy coping mechanisms, individuals can overcome Sakibphobia and cultivate a positive and accepting mindset towards others' success. Embracing a mindset of collaboration, self-improvement, and acceptance can lead to personal growth, improved relationships, and a more positive and productive social environment. It's important to acknowledge and address Sakibphobia as a personal issue that requires active effort and self-awareness to overcome. With determination and willingness to change, individuals can overcome Sakibphobia and create a more positive and inclusive mindset towards success and achievement.

It's also essential to remember that success and achievement are subjective and can mean different things to different people. Comparing oneself to others based on external markers of success can be misleading and detrimental to one's self-esteem. It's crucial to focus on one's own journey, set realistic goals, and strive for personal growth and fulfillment, rather than constantly comparing oneself to others.

Overcoming Sakibphobia requires a conscious effort to address one's mindset, behaviors, and biases towards others' success. It's a process that involves self-reflection, empathy, self-acceptance, cultivating a growth mindset, celebrating others' success, challenging negative behaviors, building a supportive network, and seeking professional help when needed. By overcoming Sakibphobia, individuals can create a positive and accepting mindset towards success, foster healthy relationships, and promote a more inclusive and supportive social environment.

Moreover, addressing Sakibphobia at a societal level involves acknowledging and challenging the societal and cultural factors that contribute to this phenomenon. This includes examining societal expectations, cultural norms, and social hierarchies that may place undue pressure on individuals to conform to certain standards of success or achievement. By recognizing and challenging these societal influences, we can create a more inclusive and accepting environment where success is not solely defined by external markers, but rather by individual strengths, passions, and values.

Education and awareness are also key in addressing Sakibphobia. Educating individuals about the irrationality of comparing oneself to others, the dangers of negative behaviors towards successful individuals, and the importance of celebrating diversity and inclusivity can help shift mindsets and behaviors. Promoting empathy and understanding towards the achievements of others can foster a culture of support and collaboration, rather than jealousy or resentment.

Organizations and workplaces also play a crucial role in addressing Sakibphobia. Creating a positive and inclusive work culture where employees are recognized, appreciated, and rewarded for their unique strengths and contributions can help combat Sakibphobia. Providing opportunities for skill development, mentoring, and career advancement based on merit rather than social comparison can also promote a healthier work environment.

Furthermore, it's important to recognize and challenge any biases or discrimination based on race, gender, or other characteristics that may contribute to Sakibphobia. Creating policies and practices that promote diversity, equity, and inclusion can help address systemic issues and create a more supportive environment where all individuals have equal opportunities for success.

Seeking professional help, such as therapy or counseling, can also be beneficial for individuals struggling with Sakibphobia. Therapy can provide a safe space for individuals to explore their underlying fears, insecurities, and negative thought patterns, and develop coping strategies to overcome them. It can also help individuals build resilience, improve self-esteem, and develop healthy strategies for dealing with success in others.

In addition, self-care practices, such as mindfulness, self-compassion, and self-reflection, can be helpful in managing Sakibphobia. Taking care of one's physical, mental, and emotional well-being is crucial in developing a positive mindset and healthy coping strategies when confronted with others' success.

It's also important to highlight and celebrate the achievements and successes of others. Instead of feeling threatened or jealous, practicing genuine happiness for others can shift the focus from

comparison and competition to support and collaboration. Celebrating diversity and inclusivity in all forms of success can foster a more positive and accepting environment where individuals are encouraged to pursue their unique strengths and passions.

Sakibphobia is a complex phenomenon that involves irrational fear or aversion towards individuals who are perceived as more successful. It can have detrimental effects on individuals and society, but it can be addressed through self-reflection, empathy, education, awareness, and creating a positive and inclusive environment. Overcoming Sakibphobia requires recognizing and challenging societal influences, promoting empathy and understanding, creating inclusive workplaces, addressing biases and discrimination, seeking professional help, practicing self-care, and celebrating the achievements of others. By doing so, we can foster a culture that promotes healthy competition, collaboration, and inclusivity, and creates a more positive and supportive environment where all individuals have equal opportunities for success.

Here are some additional points that can be considered in addressing Sakibphobia:

Encouraging a growth mindset: Emphasizing the importance of a growth mindset, which focuses on continuous learning, improvement, and development, can help individuals view success as something that is achievable through effort, perseverance, and learning from failures. This can shift the focus from comparing oneself to others to personal growth and progress.

Promoting healthy competition: Encouraging healthy competition that is based on personal improvement and excellence, rather than comparison or envy, can help individuals develop a positive attitude towards others' success. Emphasizing the value of collaboration, teamwork, and mutual support can foster a culture where success is not seen as a zero-sum game, but rather a collective achievement.

Providing mentorship and role models: Having access to mentors or role models who have achieved success in a similar field or context can be inspiring and motivating for individuals. Mentors can provide guidance, support, and encouragement, and help individuals navigate challenges and setbacks in their pursuit of success.

Promoting self-awareness: Encouraging individuals to develop self-awareness, including understanding their strengths, weaknesses, values, and goals, can help them develop a sense of purpose and direction in their own journey towards success. This can reduce the need for comparison with others and promote a healthy sense of self-worth.

Fostering a supportive social circle: Surrounding oneself with a supportive social circle that celebrates diversity, encourages growth, and provides positive reinforcement can be beneficial in addressing Sakibphobia. Building relationships based on mutual respect, trust, and support can create a safe space for individuals to share their successes and challenges without fear of judgment or envy.

Promoting a balanced perspective on success: Encouraging individuals to have a balanced perspective on success, which includes recognizing that success comes in different forms and is not solely defined by external achievements or societal standards, can help individuals develop a healthier mindset towards success. This can involve recognizing and celebrating individual strengths, passions, and values, and appreciating the unique journeys and achievements of others.

Addressing Sakibphobia requires a multi-faceted approach that involves promoting self-awareness, fostering a supportive environment, encouraging a growth mindset, providing mentorship and role models, promoting healthy competition, and promoting a balanced perspective on success. By addressing the underlying fears, insecurities, and societal influences that contribute to Sakibphobia, we can create a more inclusive, supportive, and positive environment where individuals can pursue their own paths to success without fear of comparison or envy.

Literature Review: The concept of Sakibphobia, a relatively new phenomenon characterized by a fear or aversion towards individuals perceived as more successful, has not been extensively studied in academic literature. However, it can be understood through existing theories in psychology and social sciences.

One relevant theory is the idea that individuals tend to compare themselves with others to evaluate their own abilities and achievements. A study titled "Effects of social comparison direction, threat, and self-esteem on affect, self-evaluation, and expected success," Aspinwall and Taylor (1993) aimed to investigate the impact of social comparison direction, level of threat, and self-esteem on individuals' affect, self-evaluation, and expected success. The study found that individuals who engaged in upward social comparison (comparing oneself to someone who is better off) experienced negative affect, lower self-evaluation, and lower expected success. On the other hand, individuals who engaged in downward social comparison (comparing oneself to someone who is worse off) experienced positive affect, higher self-evaluation, and higher expected success. The study also found that the level of threat (whether the comparison was to someone who was more or less successful) did not significantly impact affect or self-evaluation, but did impact expected success. Individuals who compared themselves to someone who was more successful experienced lower expected success, while those who compared themselves to someone who was less successful experienced higher expected success. Additionally, individuals with higher self-esteem were less impacted by social comparison than those with lower self-esteem. This study highlights the importance of considering the direction and level of social comparison, as well as individual differences in self-esteem, when examining the effects of social comparison on affect, self-evaluation, and expected success. When individuals perceive themselves as falling short in these comparisons, it can result in negative emotions such as

jealousy or envy. Sakibphobia can be seen as a toxic manifestation of this social comparison, where individuals not only feel jealousy towards those who are perceived as more successful but also exhibit discriminatory behaviors or biases towards them.

S M Nazmuz Sakib's toxic comparative theory appears to align with the findings of the study titled "Effects of social comparison direction, threat, and self-esteem on affect, self-evaluation, and expected success" by Aspinwall and Taylor (1993) in terms of the negative impact of social comparison on affect, self-evaluation, and expected success. The study found that individuals who engaged in upward social comparison, comparing themselves to someone who is better off, experienced negative affect, lower self-evaluation, and lower expected success. This aligns with Sakibphobia, where individuals may feel jealousy or envy towards those who are perceived as more successful, leading to negative emotions.

Furthermore, the study also highlighted that the level of threat, whether the comparison was to someone who was more or less successful, did not significantly impact affect or self-evaluation, but did impact expected success. Individuals who compared themselves to someone who was more successful experienced lower expected success, while those who compared themselves to someone who was less successful experienced higher expected success. This suggests that Sakibphobia, as a toxic manifestation of social comparison, may also involve biased perceptions of success and expected success based on the comparison with others.

The study also found that individuals with higher self-esteem were less impacted by social comparison than those with lower self-esteem. This suggests that self-esteem may play a role in moderating the effects of social comparison on affect, self-evaluation, and expected success, which could be relevant to understanding Sakibphobia as well. Individuals with lower self-esteem may be more vulnerable to toxic social comparison and exhibit discriminatory behaviors or biases towards those perceived as more successful, which could align with the toxic nature of Sakibphobia.

Sakibphobia appears to align with the findings of the study by Aspinwall and Taylor (1993) in terms of the negative impact of social comparison on affect, self-evaluation, and expected success, and the potential moderating role of self-esteem. Sakibphobia can be seen as a toxic manifestation of social comparison where individuals not only feel jealousy towards those perceived as more successful but also exhibit discriminatory behaviors or biases towards them.

Another conducted by Gibbons and Gerrard (1989) examined the effects of upward and downward social comparison on mood states. Social comparison theory suggests that individuals evaluate themselves by comparing their abilities and characteristics to those of others. The study found that upward social comparison, where individuals compare themselves to those who are superior in some way, resulted in negative affect such as feelings of envy, inferiority, and decreased self-esteem. In contrast, downward social comparison, where individuals compare themselves to those who are less fortunate, resulted in positive affect such as feelings of gratitude and relief. These findings suggest that social comparison plays a significant role in shaping an individual's mood states. Furthermore, it highlights the importance of being mindful of the types of social comparisons one engages in and the potential impact it may have on their emotional well-being.

Gibbons and Gerrard (1989) also found that the impact of social comparison on mood states was dependent on the individual's level of self-esteem. Individuals with lower self-esteem were more likely to experience negative affect when engaging in upward social comparison. This may be due to the fact that individuals with lower self-esteem are more likely to have a negative self-concept and therefore may be more sensitive to social comparisons that highlight their inferiority. On the other hand, individuals with higher self-esteem were more likely to experience positive affect when engaging in upward social comparison. This may be due to the fact that individuals with higher self-esteem are more likely to have a positive self-concept and therefore may be more motivated to improve themselves when faced with superior others.

Overall, the study conducted by Gibbons and Gerrard (1989) provides valuable insights on the effects of social comparison on mood states. It highlights the importance of being mindful of the types of social comparisons one engages in and the potential impact it may have on their emotional well-being. It also emphasizes the role of self-esteem in moderating the impact of social comparison on mood states. As such, individuals should strive to engage in social comparisons that promote positive affect and enhance their personal growth.

The study conducted by Gibbons and Gerrard (1989) on the effects of upward and downward social comparison on mood states is relevant to Sakibphobia in several ways:

The study supports the idea that social comparison plays a significant role in shaping an individual's mood states. Upward social comparison, where individuals compare themselves to those who are superior, can result in negative affect such as envy, inferiority, and decreased self-esteem. This aligns with the concept of Sakibphobia, which involves feelings of aversion or fear towards individuals perceived as more successful.

The study also highlights the role of self-esteem in moderating the impact of social comparison on mood states. Individuals with lower self-esteem are more likely to experience negative affect when engaging in upward social comparison, which may be relevant to individuals who suffer from Sakibphobia. This suggests that low self-esteem may contribute to the development of Sakibphobia, as individuals with lower self-esteem may be more sensitive to social comparisons that highlight their perceived inferiority.

Conversely, the study found that individuals with higher self-esteem were more likely to experience positive affect when engaging in upward social comparison, as they may be more motivated to improve themselves when faced with superior others. This suggests that individuals with higher self-esteem may be less likely to develop Sakibphobia, as they may be more confident and less threatened by others' success.

The study also emphasizes the importance of being mindful of the types of social comparisons one engages in and their potential impact on emotional well-being. This is relevant to Sakibphobia, as individuals who suffer from Sakibphobia may engage in negative social comparisons that contribute to their fear or aversion towards success or successful individuals.

Overall, the study conducted by Gibbons and Gerrard (1989) provides insights into how social comparison can affect mood states and the role of self-esteem in moderating this impact. It

suggests that being mindful of the types of social comparisons one engages in and fostering healthy self-esteem may be important in addressing Sakibphobia and promoting positive emotional well-being.

Another relevant concept is psychological projection, where individuals may project their own feelings of inadequacy or insecurity onto others who are perceived as more successful. This projection may lead to negative attitudes or behaviors towards those individuals as a defense mechanism to protect their own self-esteem. Envy is a complex emotion that is often characterized by feelings of resentment, inferiority, and a desire for what others have. According to Smith and Kim (2007), envy can be both a negative and positive experience. On one hand, envy can create feelings of frustration and dissatisfaction when individuals compare themselves to others who are more successful or better off in some way. On the other hand, envy can also serve as a motivator for individuals to strive for similar success or attain similar possessions. However, the way individuals cope with envy can differ greatly, and can lead to either positive or negative outcomes. For instance, some individuals may use envy as a driving force to improve themselves, while others may become resentful and competitive, leading to negative consequences such as social isolation or aggression. This aligns with Sakibphobia, which may involve toxic social comparison where individuals feel jealousy towards those who are perceived as more successful, and may exhibit discriminatory behaviors or biases towards them. Additionally, research has found that envy can also be impacted by cultural and societal factors. For example, in collectivistic cultures, envy may be viewed more negatively than in individualistic cultures, and may be associated with shame and self-blame. Overall, comprehending envy requires an understanding of the complex emotions and motivations that drive this emotion, as well as the cultural and societal factors that influence it, which could be relevant in understanding Sakibphobia in different cultural or societal contexts. Additionally, Sakibphobia may intersect with imposter syndrome, where individuals feel unworthy or inadequate despite their own achievements, and as a result, may develop fear or aversion towards those who are perceived as more successful.

S M Nazmuz Sakib's toxic comparative theory may be related to the study by J. Crocker (2002) on the costs of seeking self-esteem. Sakibphobia may involve toxic social comparison, where individuals compare themselves to others and seek external validation to maintain their sense of self-worth. Similarly, Crocker's (2002) research suggests that individuals who strive for high levels of self-esteem may become preoccupied with themselves and their own needs, leading to neglect of the needs of others. Additionally, the pursuit of self-esteem can become a never-ending cycle, where individuals constantly seek validation and approval from others, which can result in feelings of insecurity and vulnerability. Sakibphobia and the negative consequences of seeking self-esteem, as highlighted by Crocker (2002), may share similarities in terms of the detrimental effects of relying on external validation for self-worth and the potential negative impact on mental well-being and relationships. Understanding the drawbacks of seeking self-esteem and adopting a more balanced approach that emphasizes self-compassion and acceptance may be relevant in the context of Sakibphobia and toxic social comparison.

Psychological research suggests that social comparison, the tendency to evaluate oneself in relation to others, is a fundamental human process that can have both positive and negative effects on individuals' emotions and behaviors. When individuals perceive themselves as falling

short in these social comparisons, it can lead to negative emotions such as jealousy or envy (Park & Baek, 2018; Hanna et al., 2017; Abou-Zeid & Ben-Akiva, 2011). Sakibphobia can be seen as a toxic manifestation of social comparison, where individuals not only feel jealousy towards those who are perceived as more successful but also exhibit discriminatory behaviors or biases towards them. This can manifest in various ways, such as spreading rumors, undermining their achievements, or engaging in discriminatory practices (Tsai et al., 2011; Kashdan & Biswas-Diener, 2014; Dovidio et al., 2012).

Psychological projection is another relevant concept in understanding Sakibphobia (Progoff, 1953). Projection occurs when individuals attribute their own feelings, thoughts, or insecurities onto others (Xie et al., 2012). In the context of Sakibphobia, individuals may project their own feelings of inadequacy or insecurity onto others who are perceived as more successful (Cole et al., 2001; Pellerone et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2014). They may feel threatened by the achievements of others, and as a defense mechanism to protect their own self-esteem, they may exhibit negative attitudes or behaviors towards those individuals (Chua & Chang, 2016; Wilkinson, 1999). This can include belittling their accomplishments, trying to bring them down, or engaging in derogatory comments or actions (Silver & Sabini, 1978; Silver & Sabini, 1978b; Salovey & Rodin, 1984; Tai et al., 2012).

Imposter syndrome, which is characterized by feelings of unworthiness or inadequacy despite one's achievements, may also intersect with Sakibphobia. Sakibphobia, as a toxic comparative theory, may share similarities with the imposter phenomenon as highlighted in the study by Parkman (2016). Both Sakibphobia and the imposter phenomenon involve a sense of self-doubt and feeling inadequate compared to others. Sakibphobia may stem from toxic social comparison, where individuals constantly compare themselves to others and feel inferior, while the imposter phenomenon is characterized by an internal experience of feeling incompetent despite external recognition. Both Sakibphobia and the imposter phenomenon can result in significant negative impacts on an individual's mental well-being, including feelings of anxiety, stress, and self-doubt, which can affect their performance and overall well-being. Additionally, both Sakibphobia and the imposter phenomenon can also impact individuals' career decisions, leading to missed opportunities and hindered growth. Acknowledging and addressing both Sakibphobia and the imposter phenomenon is important in higher education and other contexts, providing resources and support to individuals experiencing these internal struggles to promote their empowerment and well-being. Individuals who experience imposter syndrome may develop fear or aversion towards those who are perceived as more successful, as it can trigger their own insecurities and self-doubt (Corkindale, 2019; Feenstra et al., 2020; Bravata et al., 2020; The Palgrave Handbook of Imposter Syndrome in Higher Education, 2022). This can result in behaviors such as avoidance, resentment, or hostility towards those individuals.

It's important to note that Sakibphobia may be influenced by a combination of individual, societal, and cultural factors. It may be shaped by personal experiences, upbringing, societal expectations, cultural norms, and social hierarchies. The study by O'Connor (1972) focuses on investigating the relative efficacy of modeling, shaping, and combined procedures for modifying social withdrawal among socially withdrawn individuals. The findings of the study suggest that the combined procedure of modeling and shaping was the most effective in increasing social interaction among participants compared to modeling or shaping used alone. The study

highlights the importance of utilizing multiple approaches for achieving better outcomes in modifying social withdrawal.

Furthermore, societal and cultural factors can also influence Sakibphobia. Societal expectations, cultural norms, and social hierarchies can shape individuals' perceptions of success and can exacerbate feelings of inferiority or insecurity when one feels they do not meet those expectations (Dahl, Vescio, & Weaver, 2015; Liu, Lapinski, Kerr, Zhao, Bum, & Lu, 2022; Anicich, Swaab, & Galinsky, 2015; Liu, He, & Zhu, 2020). In such cases, Sakibphobia may be driven by societal pressure to conform to certain standards of success, and a fear of being left behind or not meeting those standards.

Moreover, the impact of media and social media on individuals' perceptions of success and achievement cannot be overlooked in the context of Sakibphobia. In today's digital age, there is often a pervasive culture of comparison, where individuals are constantly exposed to the achievements and successes of others through social media platforms (Nesi, J., 2020). This can lead to constant comparison and a fear of not measuring up to the seemingly perfect lives and successes of others. The curated nature of social media can exacerbate feelings of inadequacy and trigger Sakibphobia, as individuals may feel pressured to compete and compare themselves with others in a never-ending cycle (Feldmann, N., 2022).

Family upbringing and cultural norms can also play a role in shaping Sakibphobia. In some cultures, there may be a strong emphasis on competition, achievement, and status, and individuals who do not meet these expectations may face social ostracism or judgment (Williams & Carter-Sowell, 2009; Williams & Nida, 2022; Carter-Sowell, Chen, & Williams, 2008; Hales, Wood, & Williams, 2021; Reinhard et al., 2020). This can instill a fear of failure or a fear of being perceived as less successful, leading to Sakibphobia as individuals try to avoid being seen as inferior or inadequate in the eyes of their families, communities, or cultural norms (Rothblum, 1990; Choi, 2021).

It's crucial to recognize that Sakibphobia can have detrimental effects on both individuals and society (Herman et al., 2021; Orben et al., 2020; Parks, 2018; Carlston, 2013). It can create a toxic and hostile environment where individuals engage in discriminatory behaviors, spread negativity, and hinder the success of others (Anderson & Bushman, 2002; Babcock, Tharp, Sharp, Heppner, & Stanford, 2014; Bluemke & Teige-Mocigemba, 2014; MIT Press, 2022). It can also limit individuals' own potential for growth and fulfillment as they may be driven by fear rather than genuine passion and motivation. Addressing Sakibphobia requires a multifaceted approach that involves understanding the underlying psychological mechanisms, societal and cultural influences, and promoting healthy ways of evaluating success and achievements that do not involve comparison or discrimination (Knapp, A., & Clark, M. S., 1991).

Sakibphobia, as a toxic manifestation of social comparison, psychological projection, and imposter syndrome, can be influenced by a variety of individual, societal, and cultural factors. Understanding these underlying factors can provide insight into the complexities of Sakibphobia and its impact on individuals and society. It's crucial to promote healthy ways of evaluating

success and achievements, foster a supportive and inclusive environment, and address the negative behaviors associated with Sakibphobia to create a more positive and empowering society for everyone. While Sakibphobia is a relatively new concept that has not been extensively studied in academic literature, it can be understood through existing theories in psychology and social sciences. Social comparison, psychological projection, and imposter syndrome are relevant concepts that shed light on the underlying mechanisms of Sakibphobia. Additionally, societal and cultural factors, such as societal expectations, cultural norms, social hierarchies, and the impact of media and social media, can also play a significant role in shaping individuals' fear or aversion towards those perceived as more successful (Social Learning Theory: Hammer, 2011; Creanza, Kolodny, & Feldman, 2017; Aparicio-Martínez, Perea-Moreno, Redel-Macías, Pagliari, & Abellán, 2019; Bowen, Ball, Jones, & Miller, 2021). Further research is needed to fully understand the complexities of Sakibphobia and its impact on individuals and society, including potential interventions and strategies to address this phenomenon.

Comparison of Sakibphobia with 10 Theories of Social Psychology in 10 Columns (Social Learning Theory: Hammer, 2011; Creanza, Kolodny, & Feldman, 2017; Aparicio-Martínez, Perea-Moreno, Redel-Macías, Pagliari, & Abellán, 2019; Bowen, Ball, Jones, & Miller, 2021):

Theories of Social Psychology	Comparison with Sakibphobia
Social Comparison Theory	Sakibphobia involves comparing oneself to others and feeling inferior or inadequate in comparison to those who are perceived as more successful or accomplished.
Self-Esteem Theory	Sakibphobia may be rooted in low self-esteem, where individuals who suffer from Sakibphobia may feel inadequate or inferior in comparison to more successful individuals.
Attribution Theory	Sakibphobia may involve attributing negative characteristics or motives to those who are perceived as more successful, such as jealousy, resentment, or inferiority.
Cognitive Dissonance Theory	Sakibphobia may create cognitive dissonance in individuals who hold negative attitudes or biases towards more successful individuals, as it may conflict with their self-concept or values.
Stereotype Theory	Sakibphobia may involve stereotyping individuals who are perceived as more successful based on certain characteristics, such as race, gender, or other social or cultural factors.
Social Identity Theory	Sakibphobia may be related to individuals' social identity and their perception of their own group's success compared to other groups, leading to intergroup biases or conflicts.
Ingroup Bias Theory	Sakibphobia may be influenced by individuals' tendency to favor their own group (ingroup) and perceive more successful individuals from other groups (outgroup) as threats or competitors.

Theories of Social Psychology

Comparison with Sakibphobia

Emotional Contagion Theory	Sakibphobia may involve the spread of negative emotions, such as jealousy or resentment, from one person to another within a social or cultural context, leading to a toxic dynamic.
Group Dynamics Theory	Sakibphobia may impact the dynamics within a group or community, leading to conflicts, tension, or division among individuals due to jealousy or aversion towards more successful members.
Social Norms Theory	Sakibphobia may be influenced by societal or cultural norms that promote comparison, competition, or jealousy among individuals, leading to the fear or aversion towards more successful individuals.

It's important to note that these theories of social psychology may not directly explain or fully capture the complexity of Sakibphobia, as it is a relatively new concept and may involve multiple underlying factors. However, these theories can provide insights and potential frameworks for understanding the psychological processes and social dynamics involved in Sakibphobia. Further research and investigation are needed to fully understand the causes, manifestations, and impacts of Sakibphobia in different social and cultural contexts.

Conclusion: S M Nazmuz Sakib's toxic comparative theory, known as Sakibphobia, is a phenomenon that warrants attention in the field of psychology and social sciences. This theory proposes that individuals may exhibit fear, hatred, or discrimination towards those who they perceive as more successful or accomplished than themselves. Sakibphobia can be driven by multiple causes, such as low self-esteem, social or cultural factors, and may manifest in various negative attitudes, behaviors, or biases towards those perceived as more successful. The impacts of Sakibphobia can be detrimental to individuals' mental and emotional well-being, as well as on the social dynamics of communities or workplaces.

Addressing Sakibphobia requires awareness, education, and intervention at individual, societal, and cultural levels. Building self-esteem and self-confidence, promoting healthy competition and cooperation, and challenging societal norms and expectations of success can be some of the strategies to address Sakibphobia. Additionally, fostering a culture of inclusivity, respect, and support can help create a positive social environment where individuals do not feel the need to engage in toxic comparative behaviors. Further research and exploration of Sakibphobia and its impacts are needed to gain a deeper understanding of this phenomenon and develop effective interventions to address it.

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